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OPINION

Endometriosis: Where are we today? An Anesthesiologist's Point of View

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Current Opinion

Worldwide 10 % of women in reproductive age and 25 % up to 50 % of infertile women are affected due to endometriosis [1,2]. This condition has a comparable incidence to asthma and chronic low back pain [3]. The natural history of the disease remains poorly understood although genetic, immunological, and hormonal factors are all believed to contribute to disease severity [4]. Although the majority of patients with endometriosis have a completely asymptomatic course, there is a significant number of patients whose quality of life is impaired by the disease and leads to Chronic Pelvic Pain (CPP) [5]. However, the objective findings of significant endometriosis and the severity of pain are poorly correlated together [4,6]. Moreover, it could be shown that depending on the pain treatment received, in many surgical procedures the incision size and extent of tissue trauma were not related to postoperative pain intensity [7].

The treatment of endometriosis can be conservatively in addition to hormonal treatment, sometimes combined with anti-inflammatory drugs or if conservative strategies have been exhausted by surgical excision of the lesions. In non-pregnant women, hysterectomy is the most common surgical procedure [3]. But approximately 30 % of women who undergo endometriosis surgery report ongoing pain after surgical excision of the lesions [8]. In comparison with women without endometriosis, they had a four-time greater risk for chronic opioid use and this should be taken into account during treatment selection [9].

After surgery, the overall initial postoperative pain can be severe, but generally subsides to Numeric Rating Scale (NRS) for pain assessment scores < 4 within one day after surgery. Pain generated from laparoscopic hysterectomy includes incisional pain, which can be also severe initially, but subsides within the first half day; visceral pain, which takes longer (up to a day) to resolve; and shoulder pain (e.g. shoulder-tip pain), which is milder but occurs in about 80% of women following gynaecological laparoscopy [10], typically peaks within 24 hours and can last for several days. Typical length for use of opioid rescue drugs is approximately 4 days. Despite acute pain can be controlled and mostly resolves within 1 week and should not cause distress or limit postoperative recovery [11]. As already mentioned above, in addition to surgical trauma, other predisposing factors influence the recovery or development of chronicity. As with non-surgical chronic pain, psychological and social factors have an important

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influence, which can persist for months or years after the procedure [12]. Suboptimal acute-pain management accompanied by an array of negative consequences, including increased morbidity, impaired physical function and quality of life, slowed recovery, prolonged opioid use during and after hospitalization, and increased cost of care. In addition, early postoperative pain appears to trigger persistent pain that may last for months after surgery in a substantial proportion of patients.

Especially young age, non-white race, less education, history of sleep dysfunction, current tobacco, alcohol use, high scores on fibromyalgia screening administered preoperatively, and high anxiety are associated with higher pain severity, excess postoperative opioid use and are potential determinants of persistent pain after surgery. Because pain is both a sensory and an emotional experience, psychological factors such as mood, disability and pain coping (e.g., pain self-efficacy and pain catastrophizing) play an important role in this setting [13-15]; so that especially patients with a tendency or known depression, anxiety, catastrophizing symptoms are at high risk for developing Chronic Postsurgical Pain (CPSP) [16,17]. However, for some patients with acute postoperative pain persists beyond the usual time of tissue healing and transitions into a chronic pain state. It is estimated that approximately 10% of all patients, who have surgery, and 30% of all patients with endometriosis had a chronification of pain. Typically, it begins as acute postoperative pain that is difficult to control, but soon transitions into a persistent pain condition with neuropathic features that are unresponsive to opioids and could trigger the development and persistence of CPSP. However, opioids are too often overused, particularly in the post-discharge period [12].

Opioids are usually a component of a typical postoperative analgesia regimen, and a multimodal strategy is frequently used to achieve the best outcome. But opioid tolerance, adverse effects, contraindications, or a combination of those factors may prevent or limit the use of one or more components of the multimodal regimen [18]. Especially lower abdominal surgery and other procedures had the greatest benefit in opioid reduction.

During anaesthesia, Propofol or volatile anaesthetics are mostly used. In addition, various co-administrators such as Ketamine, Lidocaine, and Dexmedetomidine and their combination(s)

have been increasingly used alone or in combination during the last decade [19]. This circumstance is reflected in the Enhanced Recovery after Surgery (ERAS) recommendations for perioperative care [20].

In the treatment of these patients' population, the NMDA receptor antagonist Ketamine may play a critical role in those patients undergoing surgery in which the expected postoperative pain will be serve [21]. For the acute pain management in the settings of trauma, exacerbation of chronic painful conditions, and postsurgical pain, particularly in patients who are opioid tolerant, Ketamine is most commonly used, generally in subanaesthetic doses [22]. As some patients reported severe debilitating side effects of Ketamine administration that did not tolerate higher ketamine doses, an adequate balance of analgesia and adverse effects in continuous low-dose in a range of 0.1-0.5 mg*kg⁻¹*h⁻¹ was described as sufficient [18].

Other components in pain management and treatment of endometriosis are the continuous intraoperative and postoperative administration of Dexmedetomidine and Lidocaine in patients at high risk for development and persistence of CPSP. Since many years, the highly selective alpha-2 Agonist has been established in postoperative pain therapy and many other indications [23,24]. Among others, these drugs have a place as co-anaesthetics in the perioperative setting [25]. In daily use, the value of dexmedetomidine is based not only on reducing perioperative analgesia, but also on influencing delirium or Postoperative Cognitive Dysfunction (POCD) and preventing it, as well as reducing Postoperative Nausea and Vomiting (PONV) [19,26-30]. According to my own experience the continuous administration of 0.2-0.7 mcg*kg⁻¹*h⁻¹ Dexmedetomidine with or without initial bolus is sufficient during surgery and improve patient's outcome.

It should be noted that pharmacological and therapy-refractory situations surgical treatments for endometriosis can be helpful and may be an effective strategy to limit the recurrence of the disease [31,32]. However, other possibilities (e.g. psychological support) must be taken into account in patients at high risk of developing CPSP. The chronicity of pain must be recognized as early as possible so that a multimodal treatment provided immediately in addition to standard anaesthesia. In the perioperative, setting all efforts should be made to prevent chronification of pain, which in turn results in an improvement in quality of life for patients with endometriosis.

References

1. Kanellos P, Nirgianakis K, Siegenthaler F, Vetter C, Mueller MD, Imboden S. Postoperative Pain Is Driven by Preoperative Pain, Not by Endometriosis. *J Clin Med*. 2021 Oct 15;10(20):4727. doi: 10.3390/jcm10204727. PMID: 34682850; PMCID: PMC8537544.
2. Bulletti C, Coccia ME, Battistoni S, Borini A. Endometriosis and infertility. *J Assist Reprod Genet*. 2010 Aug;27(8):441-7. doi: 10.1007/s10815-010-9436-1. Epub 2010 Jun 25. PMID: 20574791; PMCID: PMC2941592.
3. Khan KS, Tryposkiadis K, Tirlapur SA, Middleton LJ, Sutton AJ, Priest L, Ball E, Balogun M, Sahdev A, Roberts T, Birch J, Daniels JP, Deeks JJ. MRI versus laparoscopy to diagnose the main causes of chronic pelvic pain in women: a test-accuracy study and economic evaluation. *Health Technol Assess*. 2018 Jul;22(40):1-92. doi: 10.3310/hta22400. PMID: 30045805; PMCID: PMC6088265.
4. Nunez-Badinez P, De Leo B, Laux-Biehlmann A, Hoffmann A, Zollner TM, Saunders PTK, Simitsidellis I, Charrua A, Cruz F, Gomez R, Tejada MA, McMahon SB, Lo Re L, Barthas F, Vincent K, Birch J, Meijlink J, Hummelshoj L, Sweeney PJ, Armstrong JD, Treede RD, Nagel J. Preclinical models of endometriosis and interstitial cystitis/bladder pain syndrome: an Innovative Medicines Initiative-PainCare initiative to improve their value for translational research in pelvic pain. *Pain*. 2021 Sep 1;162(9):2349-2365. doi: 10.1097/j.pain.0000000000002248. PMID: 34448751; PMCID: PMC8374713.
5. Maddern J, Grundy L, Castro J, Brierley SM. Pain in Endometriosis. *Front Cell Neurosci*. 2020 Oct 6;14:590823. doi: 10.3389/fncel.2020.590823. PMID: 33132854; PMCID: PMC7573391.
6. Gruppo Italiano per lo Studio dell'Endometriosi. Relationship between stage, site and morphological characteristics of pelvic endometriosis and pain. *Hum Reprod*. 2001 Dec;16(12):2668-71. doi: 10.1093/humrep/16.12.2668. PMID: 11726593.
7. Gerbershagen HJ, Aduckathil S, van Wijck AJ, Peelen LM, Kalkman CJ, Meissner W. Pain intensity on the first day after surgery: a prospective cohort study comparing 179 surgical procedures. *Anesthesiology*. 2013 Apr;118(4):934-44. doi: 10.1097/ALN.0b013e31828866b3. PMID: 23392233.
8. Abbott J, Hawe J, Hunter D, Holmes M, Finn P, Garry R. Laparoscopic excision of endometriosis: a randomized, placebo-controlled trial. *Fertil Steril*. 2004 Oct;82(4):878-84. doi: 10.1016/j.fertnstert.2004.03.046. PMID: 15482763.
9. Chiuve SE, Kilpatrick RD, Hornstein MD, Petruski-Ivleva N, Wegrzyn LR, Dabrowski EC, Velentgas P, Snabes MC, Bateman BT. Chronic opioid use and complication risks in women with endometriosis: A cohort study in US administrative claims. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf*. 2021 Jun;30(6):787-796. doi: 10.1002/pds.5209. Epub 2021 Mar 16. PMID: 33611812; PMCID: PMC8251707.
10. Kaloo P, Armstrong S, Kaloo C, Jordan V. Interventions to reduce shoulder pain following gynaecological laparoscopic procedures. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2019 Jan 30;1(1):CD011101. doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD011101.pub2. PMID: 30699235; PMCID: PMC6353625.
11. Lirk P, Thiry J, Bonnet MP, Joshi GP, Bonnet F; PROSPECT Working Group. Pain management after laparoscopic hysterectomy: systematic review of literature and PROSPECT recommendations. *Reg Anesth Pain Med*. 2019 Apr;44(4):425-436. doi: 10.1136/rapm-2018-100024. Epub 2019 Feb 3. PMID: 30914471.
12. Glare P, Aubrey KR, Myles PS. Transition from acute to chronic pain after surgery. *Lancet*. 2019 Apr 13;393(10180):1537-1546. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(19)30352-6. PMID: 30983589.
13. Brummett CM, Waljee JF, Goesling J, Moser S, Lin P, Englesbe MJ, Bohnert ASB, Kheterpal S, Nallamothu BK. New Persistent Opioid Use After Minor and Major Surgical Procedures in US Adults. *JAMA Surg*. 2017 Jun 21;152(6):e170504. doi: 10.1001/jamasurg.2017.0504. Epub 2017 Jun 21. Erratum in: *JAMA Surg*. 2019 Mar 1;154(3):272. PMID: 28403427; PMCID: PMC7050825.
14. Howe CQ, Sullivan MD. The missing 'P' in pain management: how the current opioid epidemic highlights the need for psychiatric services in chronic pain care. *Gen Hosp Psychiatry*. 2014 Jan-Feb;36(1):99-104. doi: 10.1016/j.genhosppsych.2013.10.003. Epub 2013 Oct 9. PMID: 24211157.
15. Sao CH, Chan-Tiopiano M, Chung KC, Chen YJ, Horng HC, Lee WL, Wang PH. Pain after laparoscopic surgery: Focus on shoulder-tip pain after gynecological laparoscopic surgery. *J Chin Med Assoc*. 2019 Nov;82(11):819-826. doi: 10.1097/JCMA.000000000000190. PMID: 31517775.
16. Hilliard PE, Waljee J, Moser S, Metz L, Mathis M, Goesling J, Cron D, Clauw DJ, Englesbe M, Abecasis G, Brummett CM. Prevalence of Preoperative Opioid Use and Characteristics Associated With Opioid Use Among Patients Presenting for Surgery. *JAMA Surg*. 2018 Oct 1;153(10):929-937. doi: 10.1001/jamasurg.2018.2102. PMID: 29998303; PMCID: PMC6233789.
17. Gan TJ. Poorly controlled postoperative pain: prevalence, consequences, and prevention. *J Pain Res*. 2017 Sep 25;10:2287-2298. doi: 10.2147/JPR.S144066. PMID: 29026331; PMCID: PMC5626380.
18. Schwenk ES, Viscusi ER, Buvanendran A, Hurley RW, Wasan AD, Narouze S, Bhatia A, Davis FN, Hooten WM, Cohen SP. Consensus Guidelines on the Use of Intravenous Ketamine Infusions for Acute Pain Management From the American Society of Regional Anesthesia and Pain Medicine, the American Academy of Pain Medicine, and the American Society of Anesthesiologists. *Reg Anesth Pain Med*. 2018 Jul;43(5):456-466. doi: 10.1097/AAP.0000000000000806. PMID: 29870457; PMCID: PMC6023582.
19. Sin JCK, Tabah A, Campher MJJ, Laupland KB, Eley VA. The Effect of Dexmedetomidine on Postanesthesia Care Unit Discharge and Recovery: A Systematic Review and Meta-

- Analysis. *Anesth Analg*. 2022 Jun 1;134(6):1229-1244. doi: 10.1213/ANE.0000000000005843. Epub 2022 Jan 27. PMID: 35085107.
20. Nelson G, Bakkum-Gamez J, Kalogera E, Glaser G, Altman A, Meyer LA, Taylor JS, Iniesta M, Lasala J, Mena G, Scott M, Gillis C, Elias K, Wijk L, Huang J, Nygren J, Ljungqvist O, Ramirez PT, Dowdy SC. Guidelines for perioperative care in gynecologic/oncology: Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) Society recommendations-2019 update. *Int J Gynecol Cancer*. 2019 May;29(4):651-668. doi: 10.1136/ijgc-2019-000356. Epub 2019 Mar 15. PMID: 30877144.
21. Laskowski K, Stirling A, McKay WP, Lim HJ. A systematic review of intravenous ketamine for postoperative analgesia. *Can J Anaesth*. 2011 Oct;58(10):911-23. doi: 10.1007/s12630-011-9560-0. Epub 2011 Jul 20. PMID: 21773855.
22. Zorumski CF, Izumi Y, Mennerick S. Ketamine: NMDA Receptors and Beyond. *J Neurosci*. 2016 Nov 2;36(44):11158-11164. doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1547-16.2016. PMID: 27807158; PMCID: PMC5148235.
23. Kaye AD, Chernobylsky DJ, Thakur P, Siddaiah H, Kaye RJ, Eng LK, Harbell MW, Lajaunie J, Cornett EM. Dexmedetomidine in Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) Protocols for Postoperative Pain. *Curr Pain Headache Rep*. 2020 Apr 2;24(5):21. doi: 10.1007/s11916-020-00853-z. PMID: 32240402; PMCID: PMC7223065.
24. Hung KC, Chang YJ, Chen IW, Chang YP, Chiu SF, Sun CK. Efficacy of intraoperative intravenous lidocaine for postoperative analgesia following bariatric surgery: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled studies. *Surg Obes Relat Dis*. 2022 Jan;18(1):135-147. doi: 10.1016/j.soard.2021.08.014. Epub 2021 Sep 1. PMID: 34565683.
25. Xu S, Wang S, Hu S, Ju X, Li Q, Li Y. Effects of lidocaine, dexmedetomidine, and their combination infusion on postoperative nausea and vomiting following laparoscopic hysterectomy: a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Anesthesiol*. 2021 Aug 4;21(1):199. doi: 10.1186/s12871-021-01420-8. PMID: 34348668; PMCID: PMC8336323.
26. Weerink MAS, Struys MMRF, Hannivoort LN, Barends CRM, Absalom AR, Colin P. Clinical Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics of Dexmedetomidine. *Clin Pharmacokinet*. 2017 Aug;56(8):893-913. doi: 10.1007/s40262-017-0507-7. PMID: 28105598; PMCID: PMC5511603.
27. Dutta S, Karol MD, Cohen T, Jones RM, Mant T. Effect of dexmedetomidine on propofol requirements in healthy subjects. *J Pharm Sci*. 2001 Feb;90(2):172-81. doi: 10.1002/1520-6017(200102)90:2<172::aid-jps8>3.0.co;2-j. PMID: 11169534.
28. Su X, Meng ZT, Wu XH, Cui F, Li HL, Wang DX, Zhu X, Zhu SN, Maze M, Ma D. Dexmedetomidine for prevention of delirium in elderly patients after non-cardiac surgery: a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2016 Oct 15;388(10054):1893-1902. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(16)30580-3. Epub 2016 Aug 16. PMID: 27542303.
29. Bellon M, Le Bot A, Michelet D, Hilly J, Maesani M, Brasher C, Dahmani S. Efficacy of Intraoperative Dexmedetomidine Compared with Placebo for Postoperative Pain Management: A Meta-Analysis of Published Studies. *Pain Ther*. 2016 Jun;5(1):63-80. doi: 10.1007/s40122-016-0045-2. Epub 2016 Feb 10. PMID: 26861737; PMCID: PMC4912966.
30. Grape S, Kirkham KR, Frauenknecht J, Albrecht E. Intraoperative analgesia with remifentanyl vs. dexmedetomidine: a systematic review and meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis. *Anaesthesia*. 2019 Jun;74(6):793-800. doi: 10.1111/anae.14657. Epub 2019 Apr 5. PMID: 30950522.
31. Johnson NP, Hummelshoj L, Adamson GD, Keckstein J, Taylor HS, Abrao MS, Bush D, Kiesel L, Tamimi R, Sharpe-Timms KL, Rombauts L, Giudice LC; World Endometriosis Society Sao Paulo Consortium. World Endometriosis Society consensus on the classification of endometriosis. *Hum Reprod*. 2017 Feb;32(2):315-324. doi: 10.1093/humrep/dew293. Epub 2016 Dec 5. PMID: 27920089.
32. Sieberg CB, Lunde CE, Borsook D. Endometriosis and pain in the adolescent- striking early to limit suffering: A narrative review. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*. 2020 Jan;108:866-876. doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2019.12.004. Epub 2019 Dec 17. PMID: 31862211; PMCID: PMC7175958.

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